

Simultaneous quantitation of tannins using reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography

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A reversed phase high performance liquid chromatographic method is described for the simultaneous quantitation of important tannins (gallic acid, caffeic acid, ferulic acid and ellagic acid) in *Terminalia* species, using a C₁₈ column with methanol-water containing 2% acetic acid (38 : 62) as an eluant at a detection wavelength of 254 nm. The retention times of the acids have been evaluated. The recoveries provided by the method are 97.0-98.2%. The minimum detectable concentration varied in the range 0.10-0.15 µg/injection of 5 µl injection volume.

The fruits and bark of the different species of *Terminalia* trees are being used since Vedic period for the treatment of different ailments¹. The anticancerous activity of *T. arjuna* is due to the presence of tannins and flavonoid compound including gallic acid, ethyl gallate and luteolin². Another species *T. chebula* is reported to show various biological activities³. Gallic acid is shown to possess antibacterial activity⁴. In our efforts towards developing liquid chromatographic procedure for plant-drug analysis⁵, we report here a reversed phase HPLC method using photo-diode array detector for the simultaneous quantitation of gallic (1), caffeic (2), ferulic (3) and ellagic (4) acids. To the best of our knowledge this is the first report on the simultaneous quantitation of 1-4 using photo diode array detector.

Results and Discussion

A number of mobile phases were studied for the simultaneous separation of compounds 1-4 and finally methanol-water containing 2% acetic acid (38 : 62) was optimized as the mobile phase. This has been used to separate the tannins (1-4) in an artificial mixture of standards and plant sample extract of *T. chebula*. Retention times of 1-4 were found to be 3.28, 6.44, 10.81 and 22.98 min, respectively. Peaks corresponding to 1-4 were symmetrical and base line separation of these peaks was achieved. Recovery of 1-4 were 97.5, 98.2, 97.3, 97.0%, respectively. For the examination of recovery rates, known amounts of stock solutions of pure compounds (1-4) were added in the plant extract and the quantitation was repeated thrice. Column performance result is presented in Table 1.

Peak purity of 1-4 were tested using a photo-diode array detector : compound 1, purity up 0.9990, down 0.9992; 2,

0.9996, 0.9999; 3, 0.9994, 0.9998; 4, 0.9998, 0.9999, and the results were found satisfactory.

Table 1 Column performance and linear regression data for compounds 1-4

Compd no	R _i ±C V	Recovery% ±C V	Capacity factor	No of theo plate count	Linear regression eqn	r
1	3.28 ± 1.21	97.5 ± 0.31	0.25	931	Y=363.69X-4.09	1.000
2	6.44 ± 0.62	98.2 ± 0.51	1.45	2087	Y=441.14X-74.38	0.999
3	10.81 ± 0.37	97.3 ± 0.72	3.11	2949	Y=475.97X-67.19	0.998
4	22.98 ± 0.52	97.0 ± 0.62	7.74	1886	Y=1540.90X-92.29	1.000

Number of data points, 5, number of replicates, 3

Linearity for 1-4 were determined by a plot of calibration curve of peak areas versus concentrations in a working range of 2-20 µg of each compound. Linear regression equation and correlation coefficient data for 1-4 are shown Table 1. Calibration plots are linear with r-values between 0.998 and 1.000. Detection limit, determined by estimating the minimal mass of each of 1-4 that can be quantified, were found between 0.10 and 0.15 µg/injection.

Precision of the method was measured by repeating each experiment four times. Mean and CV values for the retention times and recoveries for all the four compounds are presented in Table 1. CV values were ±0.37 to 1.21 for retention time and ±0.31 to 0.72 for recovery of compounds 1-4.

The reported reversed phase LC method using photo-diode array detector is suitable for the analysis of tannins 1-4 in *Terminalia* species. The method is simple, rapid and precise. A good separation for all the four tannins has been achieved, which could be used for rapid screening of *Terminalia* species for genotypic quality assessment, drug analysis etc.

Contents of **1** in *T. arjuna*, *T. chebula* fruit (white) and *T. chebula* fruit (black) were 0.07, 2.10 and 3.07%, respectively, whereas that in **4** were 0.53, 4.28 and 4.65%, respectively. Compound **2** was present in *T. chebula* fruit (white) only at a level of 0.01%.

Experimental

Standard gallic, caffeic, ferulic and ellagic acids were used (procured through Dr. Y. N. Shukla, CIMAP, Lucknow).

T. arjuna bark was collected locally, whereas fruit of *T. chebula* were procured from Lucknow market. Voucher specimens were deposited in the herbarium of this Institute. All the solvents used were of HPLC grade (J. T. Baker).

Bark of *T. arjuna* and fruits (black and white both) of *T. chebula* were powdered. The samples (10 g) were extracted separately using 50% ethanol in water (3 × 10 ml), filtered, evaporated to dryness and finally made upto 5.0 ml with methanol for HPLC analysis.

A Shimadzu LC-8A gradient HPLC instrument (dual LC-8A pump model), controlled by a CBM-10A interface module, Rheodyne 7725 I manual injector, a 20 µl sample loop and a SPD M-10 AVP (Shimadzu) photo-diode array detector were used. A Millipore system was used for the filtration of solvents. Analysis was performed on a Merck C₁₈ column (250 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 10 µm); mobile phase,

methanol-water containing 2% acetic acid (38 : 62, v/v); flow rate, 1.0 ml min⁻¹; column temperature, 26°; detector wavelength, 254 nm, the absorption maxima close to all the compounds.

Stock solutions of standard tannins **1-4** were prepared in a concentration of 1.5 mg/4.0 ml for the preparation of standard curve and quantitation.

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